

Prediction of Pregnancy Prognosis with the help of First Trimester Ultrasound Screening

Harvy Shah¹, Kruti Deliwala², Purvi Parikh³, Dhanvi Jignesh Deliwala⁴

¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Smt. NHL Municipal Medical College, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

²Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Smt. NHL Municipal Medical College, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

³Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Smt. NHL Municipal Medical College, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

⁴Final MBBS student, B J Medical College, Ahmedabad

Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Purvi Parikh

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Spontaneous miscarriage is involuntary termination of pregnancy before 20th week of gestation or spontaneous expulsion of fetus below fetal weight of 500 gram. Approximately 12-24% of all pregnancies suffer miscarriages and most of the early miscarriages are caused by chromosomal abnormalities, and the risk of which increases with maternal age. Antenatal ultrasonography (USG) has revolutionized the management of early pregnancy failure. First trimester of pregnancy is the most important period of human development in which single cell transforms into a recognizable human being. USG plays an important role in assessing establishment and evaluation of early pregnancy. It also helps in diagnosing any untoward events in early pregnancy and may guide its appropriate management. Therefore, USG is an easily available tool to differentiate normal from abnormal pregnancy.

Aim: 1. To assess early pregnancy developmental changes in 1st trimester USG. 2. To co-relate abnormal ultrasound findings with clinical outcome, measured in terms of spontaneous or missed abortion.

Objective: To identify abnormal ultrasound parameters and co-relate USG findings with clinical outcome.

Method: This retrospective observation study carried was out in Department of obstetrics and gynecology at Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel (SVP) Hospital, enrolling 120 pregnant women with estimated gestational of 5 to 12 weeks who had attended outpatient department, fulfilling inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Results: In our study out of 120 patients 20% suffered abortion, 8% were born preterm. 44% of patients belonged to age group of 21-25yr age group, majority being multigravida i.e. 55%, of which 62.5% suffered abortion. Those with past history of abortion 56% of them suffered from abortion again especially with less than 8 weeks of gestation. Yolk sac diameter >6mm and RI >0.5 were the leading predictors of abortion.

Conclusion: The findings suggest that it is possible to predict the outcome of pregnancies based on USG findings. USG findings like abnormal yolk sac size (more than 6mm), mean sac diameter more than 25mm with yolk sac but without embryo, mean sac diameter – crown rump length less than 5mm, crown rump length >9mm with no cardiac activity, embryonic fetal heart rate <100/min, resistive index of spiral arteries >0.55 and intra-uterine hematoma- all have positive predictive value and results are statistically significant to predict early pregnancy failure.

Keywords: Abortion, Ultrasound, Gestational Age, First Trimester.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Involuntary termination of pregnancy before 20th week of gestation or spontaneous expulsion of fetus below fetal weight of 500 gram is termed as Spontaneous miscarriage. [1] Antenatal ultrasonography helps to assess the growth and development of embryo and also allows early diagnosis and management of abnormalities if any. Early spontaneous pregnancy failure (miscarriage) is unintended termination of pregnancy before 12th completed

weeks of gestation. The reported incidence is 17% to 20%. However, the actual rate may be higher as some cases may not be reported or loss may occur pre-clinically even before the female realizes that she is pregnant, in chemical pregnancy or in pregnancy conceived with artificial reproductive techniques. Miscarriage can be missed, threatened, inevitable, incomplete, or complete based on history and findings on pelvic examination. 12-24% of all

pregnancies suffer miscarriages mostly caused by chromosomal abnormalities, and the risk of which increases with maternal age. [2] Management of early pregnancy failure has been revolutionized by antenatal ultrasonography. [3] The most important period of human development in which single cell transforms into a recognizable human being is the first trimester of pregnancy. [4] An important role in assessing establishment and evaluation of early pregnancy is served by USG. [5] It also helps in diagnosing any untoward events in early pregnancy and its appropriate management. [6] Therefore, USG helps in differentiating normal from abnormal pregnancy. [7]

Prediction and diagnosis of miscarriage can be made by history, clinical findings like pain in abdomen, bleeding per vaginum or loss of pregnancy symptoms, passage of products of conception and USG findings. The decrease in level of biochemical markers like human chorionic gonadotrophin (HCG) or serum progesterone levels can also be used to predict pregnancy failure.

USG by transvaginal route is standard for examination of women with early pregnancy that are suspected to have miscarriage. One has to be very much sure diagnosing early fetal demise as a wanted pregnancy may have to be terminated. Therefore, it becomes essential to understand the parameters of both normal as well as abnormal USG findings during pregnancy to reduce the chances of error.

To assess the accuracy of first trimester USG markers to predict the risk of early pregnancy failure was intended in this study.

Aims and Objective

Aim:

1. To assess early pregnancy developmental changes in 1st trimester USG.
2. To co-relate abnormal ultrasound findings with clinical outcome, measured in terms of spontaneous or missed abortion.

Objective:

1. To co-relate USG findings with clinical outcome after diagnosing abnormal USG parameters.

Materials and Methods

This retrospective observation study was carried out in Department of obstetrics and gynecology at Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel (SVP) Hospital, enrolling 120 pregnant women with estimated gestational of 5 to 12 weeks who had attended outpatient department, over a period of 1.5 years, From June 2022 to November 2024.

Informed and written consent was taken from the patients, and study was conducted after approval from the ethics committee.

Detailed information was taken from each patient with the:

Inclusion criteria:

1. Pregnant female patients of any parity and of age from 21-36 years.
2. Intrauterine singleton pregnancy
3. Gestational age of 5-12 weeks.
4. Pregnant females with precise last menstrual period (LMP) with previous history of regular cycle.
5. Pregnant female with threatened abortion or such past history.
6. Patients willing to participate and give written consent for participating in the study.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Known uterine abnormalities
2. Females with chronic diseases like heart disease, diabetes, chronic hypertension, renal diseases, etc
3. Patients who aborted their pregnancy electively or who lost follow up were excluded from study.

Detailed history was taken followed by general examination and pelvic examination.

Trans abdomen/ transvaginal USG was done to measure various parameters. These were analysed

Results

Table 1: Age Wise Distribution of Patients

Age Group	Number	Percentage
21-25	53	44%
26-30	43	36%
31-35	24	20%

Table 2: Parity Status of Patients

Parity	Number	Percentage
Primigravida	56	47%
Multigravida	64	53%

Table 3: Abortion in Related to Maternal Age

Age Distribution	Abortion	
	N	%
21-25	4	17%
26-30	8	33%
31-35	12	50%
Total	24	100%

Table 4: Abortion In Relation To Parity

Parity	Abortion	
	N	%
Primigravida	9	37.5%
Multigravida	15	62.5%
Total	24	100%

Table 5: Abortion in Relation to Past History of Miscarriage

Past History of Abortion (Miscarriage)	Abortion	Live	P-Value
Present, n=9	5 (56%)	4 (44%)	<0.05
Absent, n=111	19 (17%)	92 (83%)	

Table 6: Abortion In Relation To Period of Gestation

Gestational Age (Weeks)	Abortion	
	N	%
<8	12	55%
8-12	8	36%
>12	4	18%
Total	24	100%

Figure 1: Abortion In Relation To Period Of Gestation

Table 7: Incidence of Abnormal Usg Parameters

Parameters	Number	Percentage
Yolk sac size >6mm	6	5.00%
Mean sac diameter >25mm with yolk sac, no embryo	3	2.50%
Mean sac diameter >25mm with large embryo	4	3.33%
Mean sac diameter- crown rump length <5mm	4	3.33%
Mean sac diameter- crown rump length <5mm, no cardiac activity	3	2.50%
Crown rump length >9mm, no cardiac activity	7	5.83%
Embryonic heart rate <100/min	2	1.67%
Resistive index >0.55	9	7.50%
Intrauterine hematoma	6	5.00%
Intrauterine hematoma with Resistive index >0.55	4	3.33%

Figure 2: Incidence

Table 8: Different Usg Parameters with Pregnancy Outcome

Parameters	Number	Live		Dead		P-Value
		N	%	n	%	
Size of Yolk sac						
>6mm	6	3	50.00%	3	50.00%	0.0083
<6mm	114	93	81.58%	21	18.42%	
MSD >25mm and embryo						
Absent embryo	3	0	0.00%	3	100.00%	0.0001
Present embryo	111	91	81.98%	20	18.02%	
CRL >9mm and cardiac activity						
Absent	7	0	0.00%	7	100.00%	0.0001
Present	104	91	87.50%	13	12.50%	
MSD-CRL						
<5mm	7	0	0.00%	7	100.00%	0.0001
>5mm	104	91	87.50%	13	12.50%	
Embryonic heart rate						
<100/min	2	0	0.00%	2	100.00%	0.04
>100/min	107	96	89.72%	11	10.28%	
Resistive index						
>0.55	9	4	44.44%	5	55.56%	0.00345
<0.55	108	92	85.19%	16	14.81%	
Intrauterine hematoma						
Present	6	3	50.00%	3	50.00%	0.1294
Absent	103	93	90.29%	10	9.71%	
Intrauterine hematoma with resistive index >0.55						
Present	4	1	25%	3	75%	-

Table 9: Comparison in Threatened Abortion Cases In Connection of Pregnancy Failure between Routine Normal and Abnormal Usg Parameters (N=15)

Usg Parameters	Dead		Live		P-Value
	N	%	N	%	
Abnormal (n=6)	6	100%	0	0	0.0080
Normal (n=9)	3	33.33%	6	66.67%	

Table 10: Spiral Arteries “RI” in Association to Pregnancy Outcome

Parameter	Number	Outcome	Preterm Birth	Pregnancy Induced Hypertension
RI >0.55	9	0	4 (44.44%)	3 (33.33%)
RI <0.55	108	87 (80.56%)	6 (5.56%)	2 (1.85%)

Table 11: Overall Outcome of the Pregnancies

Study Population	N	%
Abortion	24	20%
Preterm	10	8.33%
Full-term	86	71.67%
Total	120	100%

Figure 3: Overall Outcome

Discussion

In the present study of 120 pregnant females, the mean age of patients was 25.08 +/- 2.41 years, with majority of patients in age 21-25years age group (58%). Parity of study group 53% were multigravida. Majority of abortions occurred in first trimester and in that a significantly higher proportion (p<0.05) of abortions occurred at <8 weeks of gestation. First trimester of pregnancy is important considering that significantly higher proportion of the abortions occur in first trimester. Spontaneous abortion accounts for approximately 17-22% of pregnancies and approximately 12-15% of recognized pregnancies undergo miscarriage. [8] As majority of the abortions occur before 12 weeks gestational age that is why initial period of gestation is most vital and fewer than 5% occur after identification of fetal heart activity. [9] Risk factor for miscarriage is increasing maternal age. [10] The earli-

est proof of viable pregnancy is fetal cardiac activity [15,16]. The cut-off CRL is 9mm for detecting cardiac activity by USG. (TVS CRL 4mm and TAS CRL 9mm). Thus, absent cardiac activity at CRL >9mm indicates early pregnancy failure. Our findings confirm the same. Gestational sac should be at least 10mm larger than crown rump length10. Higher rate of miscarriage is noted if the difference between mean sac diameter and crown rump length is less than 5mm [12].

Gestational sac (GS) is the first definitive landmark of pregnancy which is consistently visible by 5 weeks of gestation, even with TAS. Gestational sac (GS) is the first definitive landmark of pregnancy which is consistently visible by 5 weeks of gestation, even with TAS, GS should be at least 10 mm larger than the CRL. [11] Abnormal size of YS leads to spontaneous miscarriage. [13] Approximately 94% of EPF occur in MSD >25 mm without

an embryo. [14] It is found that higher rate of miscarriage is seen in patients with resistive index of spiral arteries >0.55 or presence of intra-uterine hematoma. Our observation matches with the above observation. Literature suggests that slow EHR (embryonic heart rate) less than 100 beats/min, at around 8 weeks gestation results in higher rate of first trimester abortion. In the present study also, 2 patients had EHR <100 /min, and both of them had abortion. This is also supported by continuation of pregnancy in patients with EHR >100 /min. Hence, we can infer that just as cardiac activity is must to confirm viability of pregnancy, so is EHR assessment required to ascertain continuation of pregnancy and same should be assessed routinely in all pregnancies. Several studies documented that a slow EHR at 7-9 weeks gestation corresponds with high rate of first trimester pregnancy demise. [17,18]. So, we firmly consider evaluation of EHR as soon as possible in all pregnancies. [20]

Conclusion

USG plays an important role especially in initial stage of pregnancy. Being an easily available, quick, safe, reliable and reproducible non-invasive investigation. Hence, it plays an important role in differentiating normal from abnormal pregnancies and predicting its prognosis accurately. The findings suggest that it is possible to predict the outcome of pregnancies based on USG findings. USG findings like abnormal yolk sac size (more than 6mm), mean sac diameter more than 25mm with YS but without embryo, MSD – crown rump length less than 5mm, crown rump length >9 mm with no cardiac activity, embryonic fetal heart rate <100 /min, resistive index of spiral arteries >0.55 and intra-uterine hematoma- all have positive predictive value and results are statistically significant to predict early pregnancy failure.

References

1. Speroff L, Fritz MA. Recurrent early losses. Clinical gynecological endocrinology and infertility. 7th edition. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins; 2005:1069.
2. Jurkovic D, Overton C, Bender AR. Diagnosis and management of first trimester miscarriage. British Med J. 2013; 346:3676.
3. Jauniaux E, Johns J, Burton GJ. The role of ultrasound imaging in diagnosing and investigating early pregnancy failure. Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol. 2005;25; 613-24.
4. Laing, Faye C, Frates MC, Benson CB. Ultrasound evaluation during the first trimester of pregnancy. In: Ultrasonography in Obstetrics and Gynecology. 4th edition. Philadelphia, PA: WB Saunders Co; 2000:105-145.
5. Crespigny D, Lachlan C, Cooper D, McKenna M. Early detection of intrauterine pregnancy with ultrasound. J Ultrasound Med. 1988; 7(1):7-10.
6. Tuladhar AS, Tuladhar AG, Karki DB, Shrestha A, Pradhan S. Role of ultrasound in early pregnancy in differentiating normal and abnormal pregnancies. Nepal Med Coll J. 2009; 11(2):127-9.
7. Hansmann M, Hackrloer BJ, Staudach A, Wittonan BK, Telger TC. Introduction. Ultrasound Diagnosis in Obstetrics and Gynecology. 1st edition. New York: Springer Verlag; 1985:241-66.
8. Zinaman MJ, Clegg ED, Brown CC, Connor JO, Selevan SG. Estimates of human fertility and pregnancy loss. Fertil Steril. 1996; 65(3):503-9.
9. Rai R, Regan L. Recurrent miscarriage. Lancet. 2006; 368:601-11.
10. Brigham S, Conlon C, Farquharson RG. A longitudinal study of pregnancy outcome following idiopathic recurring miscarriage. Hum Reprod. 1999; 14:2868-71.
11. Ugwumadu A, Manyonda I, Reid F, Hay P. Effect of early oral clindamycin on late miscarriage and preterm delivery in asymptomatic women with abnormal vaginal flora and bacterial vaginosis; a randomized controlled trial. Lancet. 2003; 361:983-8.
12. Buss L, Tolstrup J, Munk C, Bergholt T, Ottesen B, Gronbaek M, Kjaer SK. Spontaneous abortion: a prospective cohort study of younger women from the general population in Denmark. Validation, occurrence and risk determinants. Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand. 2006; 85(4):467-75.
13. Bisset RA. Differential diagnosis in obstetrics and gynecologic ultrasound. Elsevier Health Sciences; 2013 Nov 28.
14. Kucuk T, Duru NK, Yenen MC, Dede M, Ergun A, Baser I. Yolk sac size and shape as predictors of poor pregnancy outcome. J Perinat Med. 1999; 27:316-20.
15. Pennell RG, Needelman L, Pajak T. Prospective comparison of vaginal and abdominal sonography in normal early pregnancy. J Ultrasound Med. 1991; 10:63-7.
16. Levi CS, Lyons EA, Zheng XH. Transvaginal US: Demonstration of cardiac activity in embryos less than 5.0 mm in crown-rump length. Radiology. 1990; 176:71-4.
17. Tezuka N, Sato S, Kanasugi H, Hiroi M. Embryonic heart rates: development in early first trimester and clinical evaluation. Gynecol Obstet Invest. 1991; 32:210-2.
18. Chittacharoen A, Herabutya Y. Slow fetal heart rate may predict pregnancy outcome I first trimester threatened abortion. Fertil Steril. 2004; 82:227-9.
19. Sprock VZ, Vugt MM, Colenbrander JMG, Geijn HP. First-trimester uteroplacental and fe-

tal blood flow velocity waveforms in normally developing fetuses: a longitudinal study. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol.* 1994;4; 284-8.

20. Nuaim LA, Chowdhury N, Adelus B. Subchorionic hematoma in threatened abortion: sonographic evaluation and significance. *Ann Saudi Med.* 1996; 16(6):650-3.